

Metal Chelate Complexes of 2-Hydroxy-5-Methyl-Benzophenone- (∞) Naphthil

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2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-benzophenone (∞) naphthil (HMBN) is found to be a chelating agent for Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} ions. It gives a reddish brown *bis*-chelate (pH 10.0-10.8) with Cu^{2+} , a red *bis*-chelate (pH 9.0-9.8) with Ni^{2+} and a green *bis*-chelate (pH 10.8-11.5) with Co^{2+} . The composition of these chelates have been described on the basis of their elemental analysis. The complexes of Cu^{2+} and Co^{2+} are paramagnetic and the nickel complex is diamagnetic.

THE reagents having -O-C=C-N- system have been investigated by several workers¹⁻⁵.

The present work deals with the preparation of 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-benzophenone (∞) naphthil by the method suggested by G-Reddelien and its chelates with copper (II), nickel (II) and cobalt (II). This reagent gives reddish brown precipitate with Cu^{2+} at pH 10.0 to 10.8 and red precipitate with Ni^{2+} at pH 9.0 to 9.8 and green precipitate with Co^{2+} at pH 10.8 to 11.5. The copper can be estimated gravimetrically from solution containing Cu^{2+} ions alone or in presence of Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} . The compositions of these complexes have been discussed on the basis of their elemental analysis. The copper and cobalt complexes were found to be paramagnetic whereas the nickel complex was diamagnetic.

Experimental

Preparation of 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-benzophenone (∞) Naphthil :

2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-benzophenone was prepared by Fries reaction of *p*-cresylbenzoate⁷. 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-benzophenone (0.1), ∞ -naphthylamine (0.1M) and anhydrous zinc chloride (0.5 g) were heated at 160° for half an hour and then the temperature was raised to 180° for five minutes. It was cooled and the anil was extracted with chloroform. The chloroform was distilled out from the extract and the product was isolated.

It was crystallised from ethanol. Yellow crystals m.p. 140°. Yield 60%. (Found : C, 85.38; H, 5.62; N, 4.12%. Calc. for $(\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO})$: C, 85.46; H, 5.64; N, 4.15%).

Preparation of metal complex : One percent ethanolic solution of the reagent was used.

Copper Complex :

Cupric chloride solution (0.1M, 10 ml) was diluted to 100 ml. and warmed upto 50°-60°. Excess of ammoniumhydroxide was added till blue coloured

solution was formed. A calculated volume of reagent solution was added with stirring followed with the addition of little excess of the reagent to ensure complete precipitation. The complex was digested on water bath for ten minutes and filtered. It was washed with water till free from chloride ions, then with ten percent ethanol and dried at 100°-110°. The chelate was crystallised from benzene. (Found : Cu, 8.58; N, 3.76%. Calc. for $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO})_2$: Cu, 8.61; N, 3.79%).

Nickel Complex :

Nickel complex was prepared by refluxing (1 hr.) a requisite amount of reagent solution and nickel chloride solution (0.1M) with ammonium hydroxide and ammonium acetate at pH 9.0-9.5 in aqueous-ethanolic medium, when a red coloured complex was obtained. It was filtered out, washed with water till free from chloride and then with little ethanol and dried at 100°-110°. It was crystallised from benzene. (Found : Ni, 7.98; N, 3.78%. Calc. for $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO})_2$: Ni, 8.01; N, 3.82%).

Cobalt Complex :

It was prepared by refluxing (1 hr.) a requisite amount of reagent solution with Co (II) chloride solution containing excess of ammonium hydroxide (pH 10.5-11.0) in alcoholic medium.

A green coloured complex was obtained which was filtered, washed with water till free from chloride and dried at 100°-110°. It was crystallised from benzene. (Found : Co, 8.01; N, 3.80%. Calc. for $\text{Co}(\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO})_2$: Co, 8.04; N, 3.82%).

All these metallic complexes are insoluble in water but soluble in ethanol, chloroform, benzene, ether, carbontetrachloride and acetone.

The molecular weight determined by cryoscopic method (Rast's Camppor method) was in agreement with the empirical formula weight, showing that

these chelates were monomers, represented by the general formula $M(C_{24}H_{18}NO)_2$ where $M = Cu, Ni$ and Co .

The magnetic moments of the chelates were obtained by Guoy balance method. It was found that magnetic moments of copper complex was $\mu_{eff} = 1.77$ BM, and for cobalt complex $\mu_{eff} = 1.68$ BM at 36° corresponding to the presence of one unpaired electron in the central metal ion whereas the nickel complex was diamagnetic.

Absorption spectra :

Solutions of chelates of definite concentration are prepared in chloroform and their absorption spectra are recorded using Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer in U.V. in visible region.

The absorption curve of copper chelate shows a very weak absorption peak at 226 nm, 336 nm and at 685 nm. The nickel complex shows three absorption bands at 267, 337 and 420 nm. However, the

cobalt complex spectra does not show any clear out absorption maxima. The charge transfer band trails in visible region.

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